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Research on Economics Development and Growth with Global Perspective

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Abstract

Economic development is a continuous process. it is not possible in one year, it takes many years, the impact of economic development is very long. Economic development is the right example of revolution. Economic development is the very integral part of country human life. Some countries are symbol of Economic development. All the nation should follow the path way of development. Many countries are the examples for other world. Deregulation, cottage industry, Micro finance, Motivation economic and management policies. Such economy got the destination of Economic development with steadily and smoothly. for example in china and India and Japan have the economic growth target of two percentage, through this way they achieved the economic growth and Development. Economics education is very important for every nation. in the case of economic education we can get the good status in the society Economics is the back bone of every country and society. Economics system provide the way how to get the goal of development. With the help of economics we can get the consumer price index. Economic data provide information regarding the national income and per capita income. The benefit of economic study we can prove more beneficial for the society. Economic education provide the way how the all sectors can be developed. Economics data provide the information regarding the difficulties of nation

Key words: *Economic, education Development, growth, education*

Ideology of Economic Growth

Economic growth is not roses way, it can be achieved through sacrifices and control on monetary expansion. Economic development is the dream of entire nation. All the nation, s of the world have desire of economic development. Economic development is only way which give the nation how to spend the prosperous life. Economic development is very ken for every nation. Some developed nation was backward before some decade's, but due to some good economic strategy they achieved the goal of economic development. Japan faced economic disaster after the second world, because of economic growth strategy they started the journey of development, Japan provide the professional and technically education to entire population. They adopted the good management techniques which help the Japan the started the economic growth. In the few years they achieved the highest growth of economic development. {1-10}

Example of Economic Growth

Japan economic model was one explanatory model {for entire region. Japan have the main share in Automobile and in the electric industry. China is one of great example of Economic growth and Development. They organized their economy very well. They organized all the sectors of economy Agriculture, industry, Small medium exchange industry. China started the capital projects like dams and industrial estates. China government

announced the policy of deregulation, the policy of deregulation was very attractive for the foreign investment. {2-10}

Measures for Economic Growth

Chinese governments announced many incentives for foreign investors, as a result of these policies of deregulation the Chinese economy achieved the highest growth of economic development. In the recent Chinese government adopted such foreign policies specially relationship with other countries they achieved the confidence of foreign investors. Bangladesh was the least developed countries of the world, before the some years they design the Economic policies which was very beneficial for the entire population. Bangladesh achieved the highest growth in textile sector and became the main exporter of textile product. In Bangladesh they introduced and implemented the micro finance schemes for cottage base industry. In most recent years they achieved highest rate of economic growth. Vietnam faced the economic disaster before some decades, Vietnam organized the human resource and organized the cottage industries, which create the many employment opportunities. The factor of economic development is that increase in industrialization, {1-10}

Agriculture and Economic Model

Agriculture development, promote the Professional education, these are the main tools which can play the vital role in the development of countries. Some countries are the lesson for the entire world if they work hard with spirits the goal of economic development can be achieved, if countries hire good economic expert they can achieve the goal of economic growth and development. In some countries the political stability is not certain, but in spite of all they achieved the goal of economic development. {2-10}

Agriculture Economics Education

Economics education is very important for every nation. In the case of economic education we can get the good status in the society. Economics is the back bone of every country and society. Economics system provide the way how to get the goal of development. With the help of economics we can get the consumer price index. Economic data provide information regarding the national income and per capita income. {2-6}

The Benefit of Economic Study

The benefit of economic study we can prove more beneficial for the society. Economic education provide the way how the all sectors can be developed. Economics data provide the information regarding the difficulties of nation. Economic education provide the method how to control the monetary expansion in the society. With the help of economic education we can measure the development of various sectors. In economic study the research is very important, when we study the economic researches we can get the lesson how the economic development achieved. [1-6]

Agriculture Economic Education Importance for Youth and Student

In economic education and qualifications we study the various economic models which are implemented in various. In various countries they achieved the goal of development and growth with the help of good economic education and qualifications. Economics qualifications are base of every society. Economics is consist on various school of thought. Before some decades the some countries faced depression and inflation, because of good economist and good economic education we came over all economic problems. [2-10]

Agriculture Economic Education and Society

Economics education is very vital for every society. Economics education are teaching approximately are taught in every university of world. It is the need of hour that we should get the economics education. Economics

education can bring the social revolution in any society. With the help of good economic system we can bring the financial discipline in our society. Financial institutes are the backbone of economy. Qualified economists run the system very well. An economist is the only person which can bring the social revolution in the society. {2-10}

Research Methodology and Empirical Result

I conducted the research regarding the importance of economics education. I prepared the questionnaire regarding the importance of economic education.

I talked with different categories regarding the importance of economic education.

Table:

Categories. Yes no.

Business. 3. 1

Student. 8. 2

Teacher. 10. 1

Economist. 4. 0

Tax consultant 5. 0

Accountant. 6. 0

All the audience agrees with my hypothesis that economic education is important for one society.

Economic Development and Taxation Revenue

Good Taxation system is the base of economy. No economy can be developed without Taxation system. In various countries around the world, they enforce the sound Taxation system with the intention to develop the economy and the self-reliance of the nation. One of the basic features of the developed economy is to enforce the good Taxation system which is run easily by the general public. A better Taxation system is easily understandable by the general public. When the Taxation system is complicated, it can not be successful and better for public policy. It is necessary for a good Taxation system that tax consultants provide better services to the public and tax payer. In some countries, the people do not understand the Taxation system, because the education rate is very low. In the era of globalization, we are facing many challenges. The effect of globalization is very sound. In this era of globalization, we are facing serious economic challenges. Economic challenges can be faced by the way of good economic development and education. In many countries, the Taxation system is very sound and viable. Sound Taxation can give the way of progress and prosperity. In many countries of the world, because of patriotism, people pay the tax. In various countries, the Taxation system is run on a smooth manner. The good manner of Taxation provides the base to collect more and more revenue. A good Taxation system is a symbol of the economic prosperity of the country. Good Taxation systems are very broad-based in the developed countries. In developed countries where the high rate of education, the taxation system is very understandable and favourable. {1-10}

1; Literature Review

Taxation system in this era of globalization is very important. A nation can face the economic challenge with the help of good economic and Taxation system. In various countries, the destination of development with the help of self-reliance. Good Taxation systems are very beneficial to all nations. In that case, government achieved the

highest goal of economic development and good target of Taxation. With the help of Taxation we can easily achieved the highest goal of highest gross domestic product. In various countries where the high rate of revenue tax is collected, they no need of foreign financial aid and financial bailout. Taxation system is very important for every society. without the revenue no economy can be survived. {2-20}

2: Implementation of Tax System

In Taxation system there are two types one is direct taxes and indirect taxes. Direct taxes are the taxes on income sources. second one indirect tax which is collected by the other person or individual. Taxation system is the back bone of every society, if one person income come in taxable limit he will be liable to pay the tax, in the indirect Taxation system the pay is pay the tax on the purchase on goods or the purchase of any Taxation rates announced by finance minister every years budget. During the year budget is implemented. Tax is collected by the federal authority. if the federal authority collect the tax with simple system it will rise and generate the revenue of the country. Tax revenue is the highest portion of the budget, if the government fail to achieve the target of Taxation it will increase the fiscal deficit and deficit finance. Deficit finance is the bad cause for every country economy. {2-15}

3: Tax Revenue and Economy

Taxation revenue is very important for every budget. In that case when the Taxation target not achieved according to the expectations it will bad sign for economy. Taxation is the integral part of country finance. In various countries they achieved the high target of tax income. When the Taxation are implemented properly in one country. It will increase investor confidence and stable economic policies. Government should appoint the professional person's in the tax machinery. The benefit of the professional person they can run the tax system smoothly and effectively. This the duty of all the tax consultant that they provide the guidance to the all tax payer, s. The benefit of that that they easily understand the tax system easily and easily file the Taxation return and information which is required by the tax department. Government should arrange the tax survey quarterly, The benefit of that the data can be easily available regarding the Taxation pointview. Government should establish the separate bench for the hearing of tax cases, The benefit of that the problem of tax assess can be easily solved. The Taxation education is very important for one society. Many professional bodies in world they give the professional qualifications of Taxation management. Tax consultant should give the training to all student who are the engage in the study of Taxation management. Tax culture In the

Country can be come in one country with the help of tax consultant and tax education and proper tax practice. Government should formulate such polices which is easy for all the tax payers. Some time complicated tax polices which is announced by the government which can create the problem for the tax payers. for example if the simple form procedure is announced and enforce by the government it will create the easily tax culture in the country. Good tax culture can be enforce in one country with the help of tax and financial consultant. Good Taxation provide the way of development and economic prosperous. In various part of the world they. achieved the high rate of tax revenue. In various countries where the education rate is very high, The tax revenue is very high in such countries. The reason of the high rate revenue the education rate is very high and the people easily understand the tax system. {2-20}

Research Methodology

I conducted the research regarding the Taxation system is back bone of the economy.

I talked with three categories regarding the taxation system

Categories. Yes no.

Business. 3. 1

Student. 8. 2

Teacher. 10. 1

Table 2:

Cetogory Yes. No

Economist. 4. 0

Tax consultant 5. 0

Accountant. 6. 0

All the audience agree with my hypothesis that Taxtation is the back bone of the economy.

Mojority of the audience with my hypothesis that Taxtation system is the back bone of the economy.

Conclusion

in various countries where the political stibility are very fine.they achieved the goal of Economic development.Some countries got achieved of high target of growth in Agriculture sector for example Nepal,combondia,India.Such countries introduced the special reforms in relevant sectors.Economic development possible when all the countries adopt such polices which is according to the spirite of economic and Economic development.we should consider all the sectors regarding economic development.This is not justified that government provide the incentive to one particular sector.Government should provide the equeal opportunity to every sectors.Economic development is the base of every socitey.

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